

STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION INFORMATION

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Annotation: This article describes the acmeological competence of the future teacher, the theoretical and practical preparation of the future teacher, and the quality of the integrity of his abilities.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, digital economy, acmeological position, innovative and digital, market economy, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction

The problem of improving the professional skills of a science teacher is one of the most urgent and important issues in the modern information society. Today, the cognitive efforts of many philosophers, methodologists, and pedagogic theorists are related to the search for theoretical and methodological foundations of changing the traditional pedagogical profession. In this direction, it is especially important and urgent to develop a new type of pedagogical professional skills based on acmeological and systematic-technological approaches - theoretical and technological means of forming and developing the mind.[1:176]

It is known that acmeological problems appeared in the psychological-pedagogical theory at the beginning of the 20th century. In recent decades, the science of professional skills of a mature person is developing rapidly. It is called "acmeology". This is evidenced by the opening of specialized councils for the defense of doctoral and candidate theses, and the establishment of the International Academy of Acmeological Sciences. Today, acmeology penetrates into various professional spheres of social life, it is especially important for the field of pedagogical production. There is a rapid socialization of acmeology. It began to be included in the curricula of various specialties. As educational subjects and teaching aids in acmeology, the first textbooks on this subject are being developed, which will help future specialists to develop professional skills and creative self-realization. mastering theoretical and methodological foundations and methodological ways of achieving, methods of self-improvement, ways to achieve pedagogical excellence in quasi-professional activities in higher educational institutions. The results of the research show that for the first time there is a real opportunity to use and implement the

acmeological approach in the training of pedagogical personnel. This situation clearly defines the problem of forming the foundations of acmeological competence in future science teachers as the most important component of professional and pedagogical training at the university. We see the role and importance of this type of professional competence in the development of strategies and tactics for optimal achievement of personal "acme" by each teacher.[2:40]

In the process of higher education, students understand the basics of pedagogical acmeology and form. There is the actualization of creative and creative activities related to the need-motivational sphere for the professional and personal development of the future teacher, the development of the main components of the teaching profession, and the construction of the position where "I" is a professional.

Further development of the teacher's personal acmeogram is carried out in the process of professional pedagogical activity.

In the years of independence, it was concluded that humanization and socialization of education as the main principles in the training of pedagogues in our republic, the holistic educational process aimed at improving the professional training of pedagogues should be implemented taking into account the modern achievements of education at the world level [3]. As a result, an improved system of constantly improving the professional qualifications of professors and teachers and retraining them according to modern requirements was introduced.

In the conditions of informatization of education, improvement of the diagnostic system of formation of acmeological competence of future pedagogues, creation of an electronic monitoring system of formation of acmeological competence, introduction of local-modular technologies of formation of acmeological competence, development of a methodical system of development of acmeological competence of pedagogues, acmeology of pedagogues based on a qualitative approach clarifying the criteria and parameters of individual-independent assessment of competence, improving the prognostic model of formation of acmeological competence is gaining urgent importance.[4:5]

Materials and Methods).

The historical and theoretical foundations of the acmeologically competent directions of the educational process aimed at training competitive specialists on a scientific basis are explained. The analysis of problem theory by L. V.

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Abdalina, Yu. S. Artemov, K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya is given a wide place in acmeological, psychological, and pedagogical literature.[5]

The individual approach to the teacher's personality is intended to develop the acmeological competence of the future teacher, which is related to the teacher's personality as the main criterion of value, goal, subject, result and efficiency. Because a person always chooses the necessary situations for self-development, these situations appear in his mind with the need for self-awareness, manifestation, improvement, and self-presentation, and the person develops his professional and tries to take the most necessary way for individual development.[6:40]

In the "Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" [7], a number of important directions directly related to the development of acmeological competence of future pedagogues were determined:

- preparing young people who are capable of taking responsibility for solving important tasks facing the state and society, who are patriotic, enterprising, who have mastered modern knowledge and skills, who have human qualities, as professional professions, which require new approaches in this regard use of educational methods;
- awareness of the content of legal documents, development of legal consciousness and culture of young people, observance of a healthy lifestyle, human rights, gender equality, peacekeeping and interethnic harmony, freedom of conscience, respect for languages, customs and traditions of all nations and peoples development of national-ethical values along with universal human values such as doing, socio-political and economic activity, formation of a strong civic position;

Results

RESULTS

Ushbu tuzilmada dastlabki to'rtta komponent bo'lajak o'qituvchining shaxsiyatini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish jihatlarini (shaxsiy makon), keyingi ikkita komponent uning kasbiy faoliyatini tavsiflaydi. Refleksiv asosda rivojlanish, oxirgi komponentning o'ziga xosligi shundaki, uning kasbiy va shaxsiy rivojlanishi pedagogik jamoada amalga oshiriladi va ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega. Buning sababi shundaki, inson faqat jamiyatda, ijtimoiy munosabatlarda, ijtimoiy muhitda, faoliyatda, G.P.Shchedrovitskiyning fikricha, muayyan faoliyat turlarini egallashi, ularni boshqa odamlar bilan hamkorlikda amalga oshirishni o'rganishi mumkin. Va faqat inson ijtimoiy faoliyati qismlarini o'zlashtirgan

darajada shaxs individ va shaxsga aylanadi.[8:140] Ushbu komponentlar mazmunining me'yoriy tuzilishi retrospektiv aks ettirish, kelajakdagi o'qituvchining shaxsiy akmeogrammasining istiqbolli aksini ishlab chiqish, amalga oshirish imkonini beradi. Ushbu komponentlarning tarkib xususiyatlari jadvalda keltirilgan.

Bo'lajak fan o'qituvchisining akmeologik kompetensiyasining tarkibiy qismlarining xususiyatlari

1.1-rasm.

Components of acmeological competence of a future teacher	Content characteristics of each component
Motivatsion ehtiyoj	Needs and motivations related to professional and personal development, self-improvement of the future teacher
Kognitiv	Personal and professional knowledge, qualities, characteristics and abilities related to the optimal achievement of personal "acme"
Semantic value	Values and meanings of professional and personal development of the future teacher
Mental activity	Acmeological consciousness and thinking of the future teacher
Professional faoliyat	Methods of design and implementation of acmeological activity of the future teacher
Social cooperative	The demand for professional skills of the person and activity and its development
Reflektiv boshqaruv	Methods of reflective activity related to the management of professional and personal development of the future teacher

We reveal the main important features of each component of acmeological competence of a future teacher. motivational need, cognitive and semantic value components are expressed by the personal characteristics of the teacher-

acmeologist, they reflect the essence of the acmeological direction of the teacher's personality. These signs include:

knowledge and values;

creative abilities;

pedagogical position;

professional self-determination;

spiritual-ethical and motivational-required areas;

professional-pedagogical direction and important professional qualities of a professional teacher.

Mastering the normative structure in these elements allows the teacher to acquire the acmeological competence of the person.

The mental activity component is a special acmeological type of thinking activity related to the acmeological consciousness and thinking of the future teacher.

Acmeological mental activity consists of three main layers and two processes.

The first includes: acmeological thinking, acmeological thinking and acmeological thinking, where the leading layer is acmeological thinking, which connects the other two layers and forms the integrity and systematic nature of this type of thinking.

Comprehension and reasoning are processes that permeate the three layers, without which acmeological thinking is impossible [9].

The component of professional activity reflects the nature and structure of the future teacher's acmeological activity, which is carried out through the following methods: problem analysis of the initial state of pedagogical professional skills, development of a personal acmeological project (acmeogram) and its development (conceptualization). , technology and resource support, feedback from the existing or emerging situation in the professional field, constantly re-designing their own personal development based on reflecting the advantages and disadvantages of professional and pedagogical activity.

The social and cooperative component consists of joint, coordinated actions by the teacher to implement his acmeological project in the field of education with the collective pedagogical subject.

A collective group, a professional team of public education and a professional team of public education of teachers work as a collective entity. It should be noted that in the first two types of teacher organization, it is very difficult for a teacher to implement a personal acmeogram, because he always faces the opposition of the socio-cultural situation, colleagues and the pedagogical administration. He will have to create a living environment in the socio-cultural

reality, but at the same time he must always think about the interaction of the "person system".

This component of the future teacher's acmeological competence is to find the construction of consensus in joint pedagogical activities without harming professional and personal development and to develop acmeological competence in this social and professional organization.

The reflexive-management component reflects the mechanism of professional and personal development of the future teacher in educational practice. [9:780]

These components are closely related to each other. Their implementation is carried out depending on the stage of the acmeological project. It also determines their stages in the formation and development of a teacher, in which the component of thought-activity in the aspect of the reflexive component works as a component of the system.

DISCUSSION

The main functions of acmeological competence of a future teacher are: motivational, cognitive, regulatory, creative and developmental. Like any pedagogical phenomenon, acmeological competence of a future teacher has different levels of development. In our study, three levels were distinguished: low, medium and high. These levels reflect its dynamics in the process of formation in university education and development in professional activity. It is the most important and basic secondary level for the process of training a future teacher at the university, it reflects the cultural norms of all components of acmeological competence, and the teacher can independently design, implement and implement his activities. sees that it can reflect the increase.

In the first stage (1960-1970s), the concepts of "competence" and "competence" entered scientific circles and circulation, and the rules of their application, features of their application were defined. The term "competence" was used for the first time in 1965 by N. Chomsky, a teacher at the University of Massachusetts. The semantic limit of this word is very wide today, in fact, this word means "agreement", "compatibility", "to fit something", "to be compatible". Today, this word means more "universal, that is, a set of general characteristics and requirements suitable for everyone." These competencies are directed to the fulfillment of necessary tasks within the scope of various specialties. Naum Chomsky (English), himself a linguist and psychologist, interprets this term as an intuitive knowledge of language in his book Syntactic Structures. This intuitiveness serves as a basis for the individual in acquiring the mother tongue

and makes it possible to distinguish correct sentences from incorrect sentences. Therefore, in N. Chomsky's classification, "competence" is a set of characteristics attributed to language, and it means a set of individual characteristics necessary to understand the linguistic essence of the language.

In the second stage (1970-1990s), the scope of application of the term "competence" increases sharply, this word becomes a special term and begins to mean a set of characteristics related to a certain field and is used in language theory, management, and organization of communications. In 1984, the book "Competence in modern society: Its Identification, Development and Release" by J. Raven (English) was published. J. Raven, as a scientific task, poses the question of what professional competence is from the point of view of modern society, and distinguishes and shows 37 components of competence that ensure effectiveness, and calls them "motivational ability". It is known that in 1988, during the celebrations of the 900th anniversary of the University of Bologna, the rectors of 80 European universities signed the document Magna Charta Universitarum (Great Charter of Universities). This event marked the beginning of the largest project in the history of the European education system called the "Bologna Process". Later, the "Bologna Declaration" was signed on June 19, 1999, creating a unified and equal opportunity for all in Europe, and its goal was to create a single and unified space of higher education among European countries. In terms of competence, during the Bologna process, the traditional paradigm of "knowledge" was supplemented by the paradigm of "activity", i.e., "competence" by employers in the European labor markets, as a result of which the goal of personnel training in educational models is based on the qualitative requirements of the specialist. raised the concept of "competence" to the level of one of the most important characteristics.

In the third stage (1990-2001), the whole world, in the Commonwealth of Independent States, and in particular in Russia, the "Bologna Declaration" was adopted for the implementation and development of education, one of the goals of educational reforms was to make the main characteristic of the specialist's qualometric indicators professional. the issue of competence" began to be raised. During this period, a number of Russian scientists, in particular A.K.Markova, Ye.F.Zeyera, A.V.Khutorsky and others developed the concept of professional competence from the point of view of psychology and pedagogy in a scientific-theoretical and methodological way. Consequently, the word "competency" entering scientific circulation, starting from defining linguistic identity, becoming an economic and management term, and now becoming one

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of the main goals of all pedagogical processes, shows its evolutionary development [10:345- 346]

Acmeological processes in professional development are studied in connection with the socialization processes of the individual. In particular, the internal force of such development is the conflict between the growing needs and the real possibilities to satisfy them. Within this definition, the development of the individual is considered in the most general form as the process of a person's entry into a new social environment and integration into it.

The three main stages of this process are explained as follows: - the adaptation phase (implies the assimilation of existing values and standards and the acquisition of appropriate tools and methods of activity);

- the stage of individualization (as a result of the conflict, the desire to be "like everyone else" and to separate from the background);

- the stage of integration (as a desire to manifest with unique characteristics and diversity, as well as a connection with the need for individual acceptance by society).[11:45-48]

CONCLUSION

Based on the theoretical analysis, it was concluded that in the process of forming the reflexive component of acmeological competence of future teachers, the teacher's self-awareness and his spiritual world, personal actions and situations, his role in the work process and his mental activity focused on re-thinking develops instead.

Thus, the acmeological competence of the future teacher was interpreted as a whole of theoretical and practical preparation and abilities of the future teacher to perform his professional activities competently. This definition reflects the sum of the teacher's professional qualifications, their application in practice, during the performance of professional tasks, ensures the appropriate level of effectiveness of the specialist's activity.

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